

Advancing Health Equity: Sharing Obesity Prevention Policy Data

"We believe our science should be made available to the public, especially since most of our research projects have been funded by federal funding. It allows others to explore the data from different angles, apply it to new questions, or use it in educational settings."

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Related publication(s):

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Headshots of researchers/lab pics

Our research study sought to identify local policy actions most salient for addressing health equity among U.S. practitioners, policymakers, and researchers working in the field of obesity prevention. We surveyed 195 practitioners, policymakers, and researchers from August through November 2020. Survey participants selected the 10 most important local policy actions for health equity and rated each selected action for potential impact for decreasing health disparities and feasibility to implement in the next five years.

Sharing Methodology

Our research team shared supplementary materials in an open access dataset (DOI: [10.17632/6z94cbyt2r.1](https://doi.org/10.17632/6z94cbyt2r.1)). These materials include: Additional methods and the list of policy actions with their definitions that our team was unable to include in the research article due to word limits; the survey questionnaire; and a results table and two figures that were not included in the research article due to space constraints.

Additionally, our team shared the dataset of the 195 survey participants' responses under restricted access (DOI: [10.17632/n8r43gf2dm.1](https://doi.org/10.17632/n8r43gf2dm.1)). Even though the dataset is de-identified, we had not explicitly stated in the research survey information sheet that we would share unaggregated data. We decided restricted access was a responsible way to make the data available to those with interest in this topic area and other research questions to explore with the data.

Since publication, we have received two access requests, including one from a researcher who found what they needed in the openly available materials like the questionnaire, additional methods and policy action definitions, and summary table and figures. We have also used this within our research center as an example of how to share data.

Impact

Our study helps those involved with community health understand which local policy actions are seen as most effective and feasible to implement to advance health equity, particularly in the context of addressing obesity. By gathering input from practitioners, policymakers, and researchers, we identified policy areas, such as living wage, access to early education, and jobs/skills training, where traction can be made to address obesity and advance health equity. This work can support more informed policy action prioritization and development for community health, and prompts evaluation, in particular of actions where evidence of impact is uncertain.

Figure 1
Mean Scores for Potential Impact and Feasibility of 28 Policy Actions among Local Public Service Employees and Policymakers (Left, N = 58) and Academics (Right, N = 52)*

Note.
* Axes are placed at the medians of the mean scores for potential impact (4.1) and feasibility (3.4).

<https://docserver.ingentaconnect.com/deliver/connect/psp/23264403/v11n2/s5.pdf?expires=1765994803&id=0000&titleid=72010451&checksum=781E4E5845C26EAAAC08FD95DBC4488F&host=https://www.ingentaconnect.com>

Reuse Possibilities

This provides a foundation for future research on policy prioritization, implementation science, and health equity. Researchers can build on our data to explore how perceptions of feasibility and impact vary across regions or communities, or professional roles. These datasets could also be used in public health education, policy simulation models, or comparative studies in other health areas. Beyond public health, fields like urban planning or social work could use the data to align local interventions with goals to support thriving communities—for its community members.

Thoughts on Sharing and Reuse

With NIH's data management and sharing policy, data sharing in public health has become more structured and encouraged. It seems like there is a growing recognition of the value of transparency and reuse, but there are still barriers—particularly around data documentation (including study protocol, “lab notes,” data codebook and analysis code) and ensuring sensitive information is protected.

My advice is to plan for data sharing early, during the study design phase. Be clear in consent materials about how data might be shared and document your data thoroughly. Consider the potential for reuse—what would another researcher need to understand and use your data responsibly?

Our research team is part of a larger center that recognizes the importance and value of making our data publicly available to support transparency, reproducibility, and the broader dissemination of knowledge. We believe our science should be made available to the public, especially since most of our research projects have been funded by federal funding. It allows others to explore the data from different angles, apply it to new questions, or use it in educational settings. Public availability also honors the contributions of our survey participants by maximizing the impact of their contributions.